

Data Pitch

H2020-ICT-2016-1

Project number: 732506

D6.3 Advisory Board

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Deliverable nature:	OTHER
Dissemination level: (Confidentiality)	PUBLIC (PU)
Nature	OTHER
Document URL	
Work package	WP3: Data and data providers' liaison
Contractual delivery date:	30th June 2017
Actual delivery date:	30th June 2017
Version:	1
Keywords:	Advisory Board

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Abstract

This document includes the final list of the Advisory Board members for Data Pitch as well as the Terms of Reference to which each board member has agreed.

Executive summary

The Data Pitch Advisory Board was created in order to provide feedback on the programme and ensure fairness and compliance.

The main tasks of the board are to provide strategic feedback on the programme, the open data innovation approach and the range of services offered to startups, SMEs and the broader data ecosystem.

A list of 42 experts in the fields of data driven innovation, big data and data science, collaboration between corporates and startups, entrepreneurship, accelerator design and management, investment in tech, technology compliance and responsible innovation were put together.

Out of this list 12 were invited to join the advisory board and 6 members accepted the invitation. We were aiming to have 5 members on the final board so were pleased that 6 accepted the invitation to join.

The 6 advisory board members will meet or provide feedback on a quarterly basis.

Introduction

The Advisory Board has been set up in order to provide strategic feedback about the development of the project, the open innovation approach it follows, and the range of services offered to startups, SMEs and the broader data ecosystem.

A list of 42 experts in the fields of data driven innovation, big data and data science, collaboration between corporates and startups, entrepreneurship, accelerator design and management, investment in tech, technology compliance and responsible innovation were put together. Out of this list 12 were invited to join the advisory board and 6 members accepted the invitation. We were aiming to have 5 members on the final board so were pleased that 6 accepted the invitation to join.

The 6 advisory board members will meet or provide feedback on a quarterly basis and their main responsibilities are to:

- Provide advice and feedback on the data challenges that are addressed by the Data Pitch competition.
- Assess the effectiveness and fairness of the competition.
- Assess the range of services available for digital entrepreneurs via the Data Pitch accelerator.

The terms of reference have been shared and accepted by each board member - see Annex A for the full document.

Advisory Board members

The Data Pitch Advisory Board was created in order to provide feedback on the programme and ensure fairness and compliance. The main tasks of the board are to provide strategic feedback on the programme, the open data innovation approach and the range of services offered to startups, SMEs and the broader data ecosystem.

The board members:

[Axel Ngonga](#) (Germany) *Full Professor of Data Science at Paderborn University*

Axel has expertise in the areas of data-driven innovation, data science as well as technology and compliance.

[Daniel Appelquist](#) (UK) *Director of Web Advocacy & Open Source at Samsung Electronics Research Institute*

Daniel brings expertise in the areas of data-driven innovation, collaboration between startups and large organisations from the public and private sectors as well as entrepreneurship.

[Hugo Pinto](#) (UK) *Innovation, Customer Experience, Strategy & Technology Leader at IBM*

Hugo brings expertise in startups and collaboration between startups and large organisations. He is very involved in the startup and VC community and has experience mentoring startup accelerators and is also involved in the investment community.

[Nuria De Lama](#) (Spain) *Deputy Secretary General at Big Data Value Association.*

Nuria has expertise in big data and technology.

[Rigo Wennig](#) (France) *Legal Counsel, W3C*

Rigo provides in-house legal expertise to W3C on all dimensions of information law. He has specific expertise in data protection and privacy and is interested in the translation between the technology communities and legal communities.

[Stephane Letot](#) (France) *Sales Director at OpenDataSoft*

Stephane has expertise in open data and data driven innovation.

Meetings

The above members of the advisory board will be asked to provide feedback or participate in meetings with the consortium at least 4 times within the 3 years that the program will run.

For the first call we asked the Advisory Board to provide feedback on the challenges that we have set up for SMEs to solve. The feedback was provided in the form of a survey in June 2017. We anticipate the next meeting to be in the autumn of 2017. The second meeting will be centered around the selection of the SMEs and the services we will offer to the winners.

Occasionally we might also ask the Advisory Board to sign off on reports and documents on the outcomes of meetings and recommendations issued. In addition, we would like to be able to reach out to individual members of the board for more informal feedback and advice, based on their experience and expertise.

Annex A - Advisory Board - Terms of reference

Data Pitch Advisory Board terms of reference

This document is intended as a living point of reference for the terms of the Data Pitch Advisory Board to operate under. Any part of these terms may be discussed and changed with group consensus.

1. Purpose and scope

1.1 What we do

The Advisory Board has been set up in order to provide strategic feedback about the development of the project, the open innovation approach it follows, and the range of services offered to startups, SMEs and the broader data ecosystem.

Data Pitch is led by the University of Southampton (SOTON). As part of the Data Pitch consortium, the Open Data Institute (ODI) will manage the engagement with the Advisory Board. Data Pitch runs for a period of three years, from January 2017 till December 2019. More information about Data Pitch is available at datapitch.eu.

1.2 Responsibilities of the Advisory Board

- Provide advice and feedback on the data challenges that are addressed by the Data Pitch competition
- Assess the effectiveness and fairness of the competition
- Assess the range of services available for digital entrepreneurs via the Data Pitch accelerator

As part of the competition to select startups and SMEs, Data Pitch will run two consecutive calls. The Advisory Board are expected to meet or provide feedback four times, twice for each call.

1.3 Values

The Advisory Board will seek to be as transparent and open as possible in its work, and invite views from a wide spectrum of stakeholders.

The board will at all times act in the best interests of the project and its funders, the European Commission, rather than to benefit any individual or organisation.

2. Roles and expectations for board members

2.1 Structure and size

The board will be made up of a chair person (or people), and other general board members. Please see Section 3.1 on the process of appointing a chairperson.

In order to strengthen the Data Pitch programme, the board should consist of people with experience, knowledge, skills and talents that will make a significant contribution. We will seek to reflect a broad range of areas within the sector, and in addition will aim to set up a diverse board.

The Advisory Board will at all times be comprised of approximately 5 experts who cover different areas such as open and social innovation, big industry, entrepreneurs, SMEs, business mentors and angels, legal/IP experts, and security and data privacy activists.

2.2 Areas of expertise

To be effective, the Advisory Board will need to be able to adequately cover most of the following areas. Whilst these do not necessarily need to be specific roles that individual(s) will hold, it is recommended that members' areas of expertise and focus are considered in light of the overall group balance, so as to get an appropriate spread.

- **Data-driven innovation**
 - Promote open data and standards, and providing quality assurance for the work that the Data Pitch consortium is doing
- **Big data and data science (technical and infrastructure)**
 - Ensure the programme addresses relevant topics and technological challenges
- **Collaboration between startups and large organisations from the public and private sectors**
 - Understanding the needs and the opportunities for both groups to be able to help broker and facilitate relationships that could be created through innovation with open data.
- **Entrepreneurship**
 - Ability to advise the companies on running the business and speeding-up growth
- **Accelerator design and management**
 - Understanding the needs of startups, how to scout the best one for the programme and identifying how to support their development
- **Investment in tech**
 - Establish a link between the startups and SMEs in the programme and the investment community to provide access to further funding during and after the programme
- **Technology and compliance**
 - Provide support on technical issues and compliance
- **Responsible innovation**
 - Provide external point of view on ethical legal issue, societal challenges etc.

2.4 Expectations for members

- Board members will join as representatives for their part of the sector, rather than their organisation.
- To avoid conflicts of interest, organisations that board members are associated with, if eligible, will not be allowed to apply to the Data Pitch calls
- Board members will be expected to play an active role in the Advisory Board. This includes, in particular, attendance at any scheduled meetings per call and input into the meeting reports.
- Board members must commit to being equally responsive and engaged

- Board members need to be aligned with and comfortable with the overall goals of the group, as well as the scope of the group's focus at the time of membership.
- Membership is voluntary, but expenses or remuneration for participants' travel time, when required, can be provided
- Members of the board can change over time, with an initial recommendation that board members consider a commitment of at least a year. Our assumption is, however, that the core of the Advisory Board will remain the same for the entire duration of the project to provide consistency.

3. Mechanics

3.1 Membership of the Advisory Board

Appointing a chair

The board will appoint a chair at their first meeting for the first half of the project.

Becoming a board member

Appointments will be made primarily through direct invitations. If individual board members leave, then further invitations may be made. A general call for further advisory board members should be held if the number of board members drops to below 5.

Potential board members will be provided with information detailing the board responsibilities, and an easy way to understand the planned timescales and project roadmap.

If an open call is issued, applicants will be asked to detail why they are interested in joining the group, and what in particular they can offer. Unsuccessful applicants will be notified directly.

Current board members

Board member names and affiliations will be listed on the Data Pitch website.

Leaving the board

Although there are recommendations about the minimal term to serve, membership of the board can be discontinued at any time by sending written (e.g., email) notice to the chair.

3.2 Group function and communication

Meetings will be coordinated and organised by the Data Pitch team. For each of them, Data Pitch will provide the meeting facilities as well as a draft of the agenda, relevant documents, and a meeting facilitator. In most cases, the advisers will be asked to familiarise themselves with a set of relevant documents prior to the meetings in order to ensure the meeting is useful and effective for all parties involved.

Minutes will be kept for all meetings. Who takes responsibility for these will be decided during the first meeting.

Each meeting will result in a written report, including recommendations for improvement. The report should be completed within a month from the date of the meeting to make sure Data Pitch can act upon the recommendations in a timely fashion. Where decisions and recommendations do not include personal data, they will be published on the Data Pitch website.

Data Pitch will set up a mailing list for the Advisory Board and some members of Data Pitch for communication purposes.

3.3 Meetings

- **Chair** - will be appointed at the first meeting
- **Frequency** - 2-4 meetings between June 2017 and December 2018.
- **Duration** - Half a day to one day per meeting.
- **Physical vs virtual attendance** - physical attendance is important for the types of engagement we envision. Virtual options will be provided in exceptional circumstances.
- **Location** - will be proposed by Data Pitch. Typically a large European city, most likely London, Lisbon or Paris.
- **Travel costs** - When needed, Data Pitch can provide some travel support (in the range of €400 per person per trip) to the members. Participation in the Advisory Board will not be reimbursed.